

**REALIEN ALS KULTURTRÄGER: SADOVEANUS "HANU ANCUȚEI"
IN DEUTSCHER ÜBERSETZUNG /**

**REALIA AS CULTURAL BEARERS: SADOVEANU'S "HANU ANCUȚEI"
IN GERMAN TRANSLATION**

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The research explores the translation of *realia* – culturally specific elements unique to one language that often lack direct equivalents in another. Drawing on various theoretical frameworks, the paper defines *realia* as cultural signifiers whose accurate translation poses significant challenges. Particular attention is given to the complexities of conveying cultural concepts through a case study of Mihail Sadoveanu’s *Hanu Ancuței* and its German translation. The analysis investigates the extent to which the German version preserves, alters, or omits culturally defining features of the original, as well as the translation strategies employed in the process. By focusing on onomastics, socio-historical terminology, and material cultural references, the study demonstrates that Sadoveanu’s portrayal of Moldavian life poses not only linguistic but also interpretive challenges for translators. Employing a corpus-based comparative approach, the study examines the Romanian original and its German translation to underscore the importance of accurately rendering *realia* in maintaining the authenticity and comprehensibility of the target text, thereby necessitating the use of varied and nuanced translation strategies.